

INTEGRATED REPORTING AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: A REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

Aim: *This work explores the nexus between the implementation of integrated reporting (IR) and the resultant influence on financial performance. This work is motivated by the growing call for the adoption of integrated reporting (IR). The study therefore seeks to establish a basis for influencing the adoption of integrated reporting (IR) or its rejection.*

Methodology: *The study is a conceptual paper that utilized library research and review of past empirical studies to arrive at conclusion and recommendation.*

Findings: *From the literature reviewed it was observed that there is a nexus between integrated reporting (IR) and financial performance. Although there are mixed findings*

in the studies reviewed, these can be attributed to the quality of integrated reporting (IR) which may vary across firms, the financial performance of firms which may be affected by the overall economic environment and the inherent difficulty in isolating these studies from the impact of other factors that may also influence financial performance.

Practical Implications: *This study is expected to influence potential adopters of integrated reporting (IR) on the choice of adopting integrated reporting (IR) or otherwise.*

Originality/Value: *This study is unique in its focus which is to influence the decision of potential adopters of integrated reporting (IR). This decision will be based on the perceived influence of*

integrated reporting (IR) on performance. The study also contributes to existing literature on this subject.

Keywords: *Integrated reporting Content Elements, Integrated Reporting Capitals, Firms' Value, ROA, ROE, ROCE*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Integrated Reporting (IR) is a product from the International Council for Integrated Reporting (IIRC) which comprises a worldwide partnership of stakeholders (IIRC 2021). This coalition was formally announced in 2010 (Beerbaum et al. 2020). The IIRC was concerned with working towards the formulation of a conceptual framework to guide reporting. Its main mission was to put in place acceptable guidelines for IR.

IR is a succinct statement about that gives comprehensive qualitative and quantitative in-depth and broad scoped information about a business entity in one piece. IR enables stakeholders to have holistic information that will aid investment and other decisions by just looking at a single report that is all-inclusive. According to EY (2023) top reporters have the advantage of achieving sustainability reporting goals through integrated thinking and this is the hallmark of IR. IR is increasingly gaining popularity as more firms across national boundaries are adopting and using it in their reports.

The climax of a good stewardship activity is reporting the achievements and events that took place during the period under review. Reporting puts the activities of stewardship in such a manner that those going through the report will have a good picture of the activities that was performed during the stewardship period. Gauging the performance of those charged with the affair of running a firm will depend largely on the report that is generated from the firm. There are several pictures that can be deduced from the annual report of firms ranging from profitability to state of the assets and liabilities or even the effect on the environment amongst others. Although reports could be quantitative or qualitative, the scope and depth of it will go a long way to give a holistic view of the affairs of the firm.

Firms reporting could affect financial performance either positively or negatively depending on the information disclosed. Prior to the reporting, if a firm sees the need to report or is mandated to report its activities in given areas of the business, it tends to strive to ensure that the report it will deliver conforms to the stipulated requirements and meet the legitimate expectation of stakeholders as posited by legitimacy theorists (Suchman, 1995; Fernando and Lawrence 2014; Udofia et al. 2020; Garcia-Sanchez et al. 2020). This action on its own helps to position the firm to perform better in the areas it wishes to report and this consequently enhances performance which is the basic legitimate expectation of shareholders and other stakeholders. Similarly, information disclosed during the activities of a firm could affect its performance on the stock market depending on the efficiency of the market. Market value of stocks of firms have increased or plummeted as a result of information that is available to the market during firm activities even though it is yet to officially report at the year-end of its activities. Finally, after the year-end report, stakeholders tend to react to report of firms

depending on their perception of this report and this also affects its performance on the stock market.

Despite the growing acceptance inside integrated reporting worldwide, some firms are yet to adopt it and have continued to produce stand-alone sustainability, corporate social responsibility or other stand-alone reports. These stand-alone reports, despite their relevance and usefulness for decision-making, have received criticism for being reported in ways that users find it difficult to comprehend, relate and evaluate current and future performance of firms (Altarawneh & Al-Halalmeh 2020). This study therefore examines IR and financial performance of firms.

2. PERFORMANCE

The performance of an organization is the first to be evaluated by stakeholders and constitute the most important attraction to people. It is therefore expected that managers who are saddled with the task for running companies must ensure that they improve their performance. A firm's improvement process is not achievable without measuring its outcomes. Therefore, establishing a measure for measuring the achievement of a firm allows comparison of performances across firms and periods. Al-Matari et al. (2014) posited that several yardsticks for measuring performance of a firm exist. They could be financial or non-financial, book based or market-based. Also, Shahria (2023) posited that ROA and ROE have positive association with firms' disclosure as the generalized hypothesis. However, several studies have used ROCE, ROA, ROE and other measures to measure performance.

3. BACKGROUND ON INTEGRATED REPORTING

IR concept was initiated through the corporate governance report produced in South Africa in 2009 and this was adopted by the Johannesburg Stock Exchange for all firms making the country the first to implement integrated reporting (Gulcin, Tugce, & Figen 2017). Stakeholders have varying time and abilities to read and analyze complex reports. Firms worldwide complain about the regulatory reporting burden and users too, complain about the complexity, length and boiler-plate nature of documents produced. There seems to be no one that is satisfied in the reporting supply chain with the totality of information available to them for decision making (KPMG 2012). Although there seems to be no much difference over the years, many authors have posited that the identified gaps can be filled by the adoption of IR through the delivery of a basis for firms to clarify their creation of value effectively and reporting them in format that it can be related. According to KPMG (2012) IR can help users see beyond the immediate results to get perfect picture on the long run value. IR places the responsibility of telling the entities story on the reporter instead of a set of reporting rules.

IR is about integrated thinking and ironically not about reporting (Deloitte 2015). Integrated reporting promotes integrated thinking and view to the various situations in the firm that needs to be reported. According to Deloitte (2015), integrated thinking involves reflection by a firm of the associations between its components, and the capitals that the firm uses.

ISO 26000 and IR are complementary. They both encourage organizations to contemplate how their operations, governance and strategy works in creating outcomes which are of high

value to the firm, society and other stakeholders (International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2015). IR remains a safe haven for objective reporting in the financial statements that can be reconciled with the analysis produced by management (KPMG 2012). Launched in December 2013, IR framework encourages holistic thinking and consequently decisions that hinges on the creation of value with the aim of increasing efficiency and productivity of invested capital for financial stability and sustainability. IR gives a balanced scorecard Kaplan and Norton (1996). It balances qualitative and quantitative as well as financial and non-financial facts. IR framework is principles-base and stipulates how integrated reports should be presented. The framework requires that integrated reports should be guided by seven principles (OECD 2014; IIRC 2021). They include: **Strategic Focus and Future Orientation**; this should give understanding entering the firm's tactics as well as relates it with the firm's capacity to create wealth. Strategy is the schemes or maneuvers that are carried out to achieve the objective of the firm. This has to be broken down into periods which should be reported in the integrated report. **Connectivity of Information**; A full view of the dependencies, mixture and interrelatedness amongst the dynamics that affects The business's capacity to add value should be captured in the integrated report. It is necessity because coordination of factors that affects the formation of wealth is critical to the survival of the organization and should be seen in the report as this also engenders integrated thinking in decision making. **Stakeholder Relationships**; IR should give awareness to the nature of a firm's relationships as it affects stakeholders. It should include the extent to which a company understands its stakeholder's interest and needs. **Materiality**; this refers to issues that are of significant nature to the organization or substantially affects the organization's activities. IR should reveal information about issues that substantially affects its ability to produce wealth over time. **Conciseness**; amongst the aims of IR is to produce reports that are less cumbersome to understand. Therefore it is expected that integrated reports should be succinct even though it should cover all the capitals. The report should show the full picture of the organization without unnecessarily boring the users of the report with details that are capable of distracting the user from the main objects of the report. **Reliability and Completeness**; Reliability and completeness are very important ingredients in a report. If key issues are omitted from a report it makes it to fall short of being a quality report. Also, reports cannot be said to be reliable if they are not complete. Integrated report therefore should contain matters of significance, pleasant and unpleasant and should be such that stakeholders will have confidence in it. **Consistency and comparability**; the IR information should be disclosed on a base that is stable over time in ways that allows comparison with other firms. An inconsistent report cannot be related across periods or companies. Therefore it is vital that to achieve this aim firms should ensure that same parameters and measures are used consistently.

4. IR CONTENT ELEMENTS

IIRC (2021) stipulates the following elements:

4.1 Organizational Overview and External Environment

This aspect of the report gives the essential context to the users of the report (KPMG 2012). IR should contain what the firm does and the circumstance under which it operates. An overview of the organization should explain the mission of the organization and the related threats and opportunities that exist in the external environment (IIRC 2021). Reporting this aspect to stakeholders will help them have a panoramic view of the firm and its units and be able to relate it with the ever changing environment.

4.2 Governance

This should include how governance works in the organization, explanation of the governance structure of the firm and how this supports its capacity to generate value for the firm (IIRC 2021). Understanding the governance structure of the firm can help stakeholders to have more confidence in the activities of the firm. This is achievable if this aspect is adequately reported in the reports given by the firm.

4.3 Business Model

According to IIRC (2021), the business model of the organization should be incorporated in the integrated report. This will help stakeholders comprehend and appreciate the decisions taken in the course of the operation of the organization and consequently foster legitimacy and confidence in the view of stakeholders. This aspect of the report provides important context to the report users. It gives the bases for more specific disclosures.

4.4 Risks and Opportunities

This aspect of the report explains the external dynamics affecting the firm, both negatively and positively and how the firm identifies and reacts to it (KPMG 2012). Integrated reports should therefore highlight the risks and opportunities and the efforts the firm is putting to deal with them over time. Even in the event of unfavorable economic downturn and uncertainties a report that reassures stakeholders about measures taking to mitigate the inherent risks could be encouraging and can enhance the confidence of stakeholders.

4.5 Strategy and Resource Allocation

This segment explains the vision of the firm and how it will reach its destination (KPMG 2012). An important element in the IR is the report about the destination of the organization and how it intends to get there. This should also include the resources needed and allocated in this regard (IIRC 2021). Information about this aspect in a report is capable of attracting investors and funding to the firm especially if the strategy is attractive to them.

4.6 Performance

This aspects explains the level to which the firm has met its tactical aims in the period it is reporting (KPMG 2012). Information on this segment should cover effects on the capitals. Improvement in the performance of the firm is a legitimate expectation of shareholders. Even other stakeholders are interested in this aspect of the report. Reporting the capitals will enable the stakeholders relate the increase in a capital to a corresponding decrease in another capital. Relating the capitals provides more insight to the activities of the firm and consequently aids the understanding of reports.

4.7 Outlook

Future outlook reports should serve as a base for users to form their independent opinion as it relates to prospects and risks that the firm will encounter (IIRC 2021). Understanding the

business outlook from the report provided by firms can help stakeholders especially providers of funds to hedge against unfavorable situations.

4.8 Basis of Presentation

Basis of the presentation of the report should be a key element in an integrated report. It should present how the organization defines matters to put in the IR report and how they are measured (IIRC 2021). Consistent application of a base of preparing financial statements aids comparison across firms in the same industry and across periods. It also boost investors confidence.

5. THE SIX CAPITALS OF INTEGRATED REPORTING

The resources needed for an organization to survive can be classified into six capitals (OECD 2014; Garcia-Sanchez et al. (2020); IIRC 2021). These capitals can be transformed from one form to other forms of capitals during the operation of the firm. The six capitals are the terms used to categorize the resources that a firm needs in the broadest categorization as distinct from the 3Ps' often used to refer to people, planet and profit (Deloitte 2015). IR requires that these six capitals should be adequately reported in the reports of firms so that stakeholders could be informed of the transformation that has taken place among the capitals and therefore have a good comprehension of the state of affairs of the firm. The capitals are discussed below:

5.1 Financial Capital

This is the fund that is obtained through borrowing, equity or grants. It could also be gotten through the operation or investments of the organization. These pools of funds are available for the process of manufacturing things or the delivery of offerings (Garcia-Sanchez et al. 2020; IIRC 2021). This form of capital is quantitative in nature and the most reported of all the six capitals. This stems from the regulatory requirements of most countries that require it as part of the returns filed by companies annually.

5.2 Manufactured Capital

This refers to factory-made items that are accessible to a business for utilization in the manufacturing of products or the delivery of services. (Garcia-Sanchez et al. 2020; IIRC 2021). However, manufactured capital comprises assets created by the firm for its own use or for sale.

5.3 Intellectual Capital

This denotes firm's asset such as implicit knowledge, procedures, protocols, systems as well as copyrights, patents and licenses (IIRC, 2021). Muhi et al. (2023) explained intellectual capital as an intangible asset that have become important as tangible asset in firms.

5.4 Human Capital

The term "human capital" was first used in 1958 by J. Mincer even though T. Shuts and G. Becker were considered as the founders of the modern theory of human capital (Soboleva et al. 2019). They see human capital as a productive factor that can affect the results of business organizations. Human capital refers to the capabilities of the work force and their experiences. It includes their motivation among others (Garcia-Sanchez et al. 2020; IIRC 2021).

5.5 Social and Relationship Capital

This refers to associations and networks that a company has at its disposal. Social and relationship capital includes: major stakeholder relations (Garcia-Sanchez et al. 2020; IIRC 2021).

5.6 Natural Capital

All environmental resources, both renewable and nonrenewable, as well as production methods that support a company's past, present and future profitability are referred to as natural capital. They include water, air, land, forests, minerals, biodiversity and ecosystem health (Garcia-Sanchez et al. 2020; IIRC 2021)

6. BENEFITS OF INTEGRATED REPORTING

Deloitte (2015) enumerated the advantages of IR to include: enhance quality of reports and consequently improve the confidence of stakeholders in reports generated by firms. Benefits of IR also includes: Improved stakeholders engagement, increased transparency and accountability, enhanced decision making and reduced risks. Muhi et al. (2023) suggested that IR will enhance better decision making in resource allocation, cost reduction and improved management of risk.

7. CONCERNS ABOUT THE ADOPTION OF INTEGRATED REPORTING

Some concerns have been put forward by respondents to the IIRC framework. They include the following: competitiveness concerns, disclosing business model without exposing commercially-sensitive information, determination of material issues, firms identification and prioritization of material elements when dealing with stakeholders with diverse interest, monetization and quantification of the capitals, relating IR to existing reports and the transition of environmental report where ESG legislation is in place (OECD 2014). Although some of these concerns have been addressed, there is still need for further clarification on some of the issues raised to guide countries that will adopt the use of IR in the future.

8. CHALLENGES OF THE ADOPTION ON IR IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

The challenges that African companies face in the adoption of IR include: Lack of consciousness and understanding of IR; Lack of adequate skills, capacity and resources to implement IR; and Lack of regulatory support for IR. Others are absence of information and information on non-financial execution, high cost of preparing IR amongst other. Also, Akpan et al. (2022) enumerated the following as challenges of the adoption of IR: Lack of knowledge of IR; Lack of capacity and resources to implement IR; Lack of regulatory support for IR; Resistance to change from traditional reporting practices; and Cost of putting into practice IR.

9. OVERCOMING THE CHALLENGES OF THE ADOPTION OF IR IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

There are a number of things that can be done to overcome the challenges of adopting IR in developing countries. These include: Increasing awareness and understanding of IR among companies and stakeholders. This can be done through educational and training programs, as well as by promoting the benefits of IR; providing companies with the capacity and resources

to implement IR. This can be done through government support, as well as by partnering with international organizations and accounting professional bodies; developing a regulatory framework that supports IR. This would create a more enabling environment for IR; Encouraging companies to embrace change and adopt new reporting practices. This can be done by highlighting the benefits of IR and by providing incentives for companies to adopt IR; Subsidizing the cost of implementing IR. This would make IR more affordable for companies.

10. REVIEWS ON INTEGRATED REPORTING AND PERFORMANCE OF FIRMS

Islam (2020) investigated the nexus amongst IR and firm performance in Bangladesh. 20 businesses that quoted on the Dhaka Interaction between 2015 and 2018 were used while pooled OLS regression was done to analyze the data collected. Results showed that IR was positively and significantly associated to performance.

Cooray et al. (2020) carried out a study in Sri Lanka to find out the nexus among IR and firm value using a disclosure checklist for 117 firms. Content analysis was conducted and then two regression models were assessed. The study found an increasing trend in adopting an international integrated reporting framework in corporate reports including the content elements but this has not significantly affected the firm's value.

Adegboyegun et al. (2020) examined IR and performance. He studied 13 banks in Nigeria and used profit after tax as proxy for performance while IR index is a blend reporting on sustainability and finances. He focused on the period of 10 years from 2009 to 2018. Findings revealed that although IR lacks a substantial relationship with firm short-term performance, it however has a significant effect Ultimately. The study of Adegboyegun et al. (2020) seems to be flawed by the period he used for his study. This is because the first framework that guides and stipulates the elements and capitals to be reported in an integrated report came into existence in 2013 when it was first published. Although South Africa from where IR originated started the implementation of IR before 2013, however that cannot be said of Nigeria that up till date has no statute or law on IR. In the opinion of this study the earliest date for the period he used should have been 2014 and this would have had a noteworthy influence on the research.

Oyedokun et al. (2021) investigated the relationship between IR and financial performance in Nigerian deposit money banks. DMO's. Findings indicated that IR had a significant association with financial performance. It was recommended that DMO's should adopt IR to improve on the deficiencies inherent in the traditional method of reporting.

Velte (2022) did an archival study on IR by reviewing the primary factors and how they affect company value. 85 quantitative studies were selected and result showed that adoption of IR leads to enhance financial and non-financial performance.

Songini et al. (2023) reviewed the most advanced researches on a decade of IR with the view of finding the implications of IR in the study's section on business value. The study found 21 works and discovered that most studies were majorly done between 2016 and 2019. However, previous researches was found to account for empirical studies.

Jayasiri et al. (2023) did a 12 years review of IR articles that were published by journals in management, money and accounting on the Deans Council for Australian Business between

2009 and 2020. 210 papers published in 64 journals were examined. Findings revealed that more researches are conducted in practice compared to normative researches in the past.

Shahria (2023) explored the affinity between IR and firm performance using 41 firms from Bangladesh. The study found that IR is positively significant in its connection to the performance of the company. It also found that businesses are increasingly disclosing IR elements in the sampled firms and therefore encouraged the adoption of IR.

Bogeanu-Popa and Man (2023) embarked on a study to find answers to the influence of financial performance on IR in Romanian banks. 19 banks were used and findings showed that while the social component of IR does not impact nonperforming loan which is the proxy for financial performance, financial and environmental information components of IR influences the rate of nonperforming loan.

Priyadarshani et al. (2023) explored the effect of IR on the significance of values in corporate disclosure. 121 firms in Colombo exchange were evaluated covering 2012 to 2019. Findings revealed that a low level of corporate disclosure exist and this does not enhance the value relevance.

11. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is a conceptual paper that utilized library research and review of past empirical studies to arrive at conclusion and recommendation.

12. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from the literature reviewed revealed that a nexus exist between IR and financial performance. Although there are mixed findings in the studies reviewed, these can be attributed to the quality of IR which may vary across firms, the financial performance of firms which may be affected by the overall economic environment and the inherent difficulty in isolating these studies from the impact of other factors that may also influence financial performance.

13. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examined IR and financial performance of firms. From the literature reviewed so far it was observed that there is a nexus between IR and financial performance. Although there are mixed findings in the studies reviewed, these can be attributed to the quality of IR reporting which may vary across firms, the financial performance of firms which may be influenced by the overall economic environment and the inherent difficulty in isolating these studies from the impact of other factors that may also affect financial performance. Even though there are mixed results the advantage of adopting and implementing IR cannot be over emphasized given the numerous benefits to shareholders and other stakeholders. This study therefore recommends the adoption of IR.

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Authors' contributions

All the authors has committed to be accountable for all the components of this work.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All the authors has declared that there aren't any competing interests in this study.

Declarations: The authors confirm that this work is a unique creation. and hasn't been released anywhere else. It is also not before any journal for consideration.

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